

What's the Big IDEA? Co-designing Engineering Outreach with Inclusivity, Diversity, Equity and Accessibility in mind

Appendix A

A scoping review was conducted in the early stages of the project, consisting of 3 main categories: IDEA and inclusive principles in outreach, Holistic Outreach Design, and Pedagogy. A summary of the resources found is provided in Table 3, along with references provided in the footnotes.

Table 1. A Table summarising the scoping review for the IDEA-Informed Outreach Framework

Resource Title	Conclusions/ Impact/ Recommendations
IDEA in Outreach	
Engineering UK: Making engineering engagement inclusive (Engineering UK, 2021)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Don't talk about engineering subjects being harder • Don't say BAME, rather refer to the specific minority group/s • Avoid saying "disadvantaged", "under-served" or "hard to reach" rather say under-represented • Avoid saying boys or girls, instead so young people/students • Young people should see themselves represented in both professional role models and the other young people who participate • Make communication as clear and straight forward as possible using plain English • Consider communication needs such as subtitles, audio descriptions and BSL • Consider visual accessibility such as lighting and sound
Equiliteach (EqualiTeach, 2026)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Empower young people to lead in talking about issues important to them, giving them a sense of agency in asking what they want to say or do • Be self-critical and aware of biases in creating content (think about the imagery and colours) • Be actively intersectional: not all feminist or gender-neutral material is fully inclusive • Challenge stereotypes when they are shared by young people by encouraging them to reflect on biases. Prompt by asking "that's interesting you say that, can you share why you think that?" • Demonstrate role models who defy common stereotypes • Share your lived experiences, inspirations and journey into STEM to demonstrate that they are not always linear or academic
Including Children with Autism in Afterschool Settings (Boston Children's Museum, 2012)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Make students aware of the plan for the day in advance so they know what to expect. Transitions and changes in routine can be difficult for some students • If giving directions for a task, break them up into short, simple statements for clarity and check that you are understood by everyone • Check in with teachers for support on what is helpful, interesting or problematic - reward systems of stickers? • Provide gloves if using glue or alternative adhesives. Consider pre-cutting some materials etc. • Consider how structured the workshop is as 'bending the rules' can be difficult. Similarly, asking too open-ended questions can be difficult. Better give a few options • Don't exclude students who have behavioural issues, rather, try to encourage interaction in a safe way for that student

<p>Making Science Personal: Inclusivity-Driven Design for General Education Courses (O'Donnell et al., 2021)</p>	<p>Establishing norms: explicitly acknowledge under-represented voices whether through videos/spoken examples. (e.g. share a life story of a scientist/roboticist and the barriers they faced and overcame)</p> <p>Active learning: Ask students to consider the skills they think are helpful to science/robotics/engineering. Ensure responses are displayed visibly. Make it clear that skills are things you can change over time. Give examples on which skills were needed for different science/robotics endeavours that are relatable.</p> <p>Make it clear that science/robotics is for everyone (people who are creative but don't like leading, people who like communicating but not creating etc.)</p> <p>Make it clear that no one person has all the skills that the students would have listed to highlight that there is no set path or key skills to this discipline</p> <p>Allow the students to reflect on how their existing skills fit within science/robotics</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Opportunities to self-reflect: examples given include asking students to think about/write down what they believe but cannot see
<p>An exploration of guide's roles in STEM outreach activities: A Contribution to Students' Motivation for Career Aspirations? (Vennix et al., 2022)</p>	<p>Talks about the 3 motivational needs of students and how these can be provided by STEM ambassadors:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Competence: Provided by strong activity objectives that make activities clear, relevance to real world problems and well structured feedback • Autonomy: Use a variety of contexts and the impact of the work, take student perspectives into account and offer them choice • Relatedness: Communication and collaboration between ambassadors and other students
<p>Designing for Success in STEM Pathways (The Institute for Broadening Participation, 2016)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aiming outreach at younger students often positively affects access to STEM occupations • Creating authentic science engagement rather than 'uninspiring introductory courses • Active learning and problem solving, culturally relevant pedagogy and science content, mentoring programs and role models
<p>Inclusive Language guide, EDI Checklist and IDEA Guide (FEMA, 2025; KASA, 2006)</p>	<p>Checklists for language to include/exclude, similar to guidelines from Engineering UK</p>

Holistic Outreach Design

<p>Tools and Approaches for Transforming Museum Experience (Brackett et al., 2020)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Brainstorming structure (How might we questions) would be good for framing the ILOs for the engineers and making sure they've covered these • Our blanket ILOs will have some 'how might we' questions off the bat
<p>The Agile management Deck ('The Agile Inception Deck', 2010)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tool for structuring project briefing, need to cover these 10 questions with engineers to show what is in scope or out of scope • Can we apply versions of these questions into the steps the engineers need to follow for the outreach box? Mix this in with some double diamond methodology into the pitch deck • Why are we here? What are the main ILOs we want to focus on etc.

Creative facilitation (Better Evaluation, 2023)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All about workshop balance, should be a mix of reflection, participation and active teaching • Might be covered by the super skills section, roleplaying and empathy to create connection to certain objectives and stakeholders. • Could create a roleplay activity during training to showcase how teaching style needs to change based on students' needs
Double diamond (The Double Diamond, 2025)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Classic design ideology that will be the basis of the workshop structure
Miro boards (Miro, 2026)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Useful tool for online facilitation
Pedagogy	
A Taxonomy for Learning, Teaching, and Assessing: A Revision of Bloom's Taxonomy of Educational Objective (Armstrong, 2010; Bloom, 1956)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Action words should be used to describe the learning objectives • Extended learning should draw learners up the taxonomy pyramid
Outreach guide to working with schools and colleges (Macdonald, 2004)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engage with teachers • Make connection to curriculum • Approach schools through 'The Teacher in charge of [science]', and consider contacting local education authorities
A Review of Effective Teaching Practices in Secondary Education (Carter et al., 2023)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Students show a reduction in engagement into secondary school compared to primary. This is attributed to a poor fit between the individual and the environment and a loss in autonomy. • Quality of teaching is attributed to: 1. classroom culture (supportive learning environments, positive behavioural expectations) 2. Instruction (lesson facilitation, checks for understanding, feedback and critical thinking) 3. Socioemotional skills (autonomy, perseverance, social & collaboration skills) • We need to acknowledge and accommodate Individual Education Plans for attending students
Creating a Classroom Environment that Promotes Student Autonomy (Highland, 2024)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Differentiate instruction - either the process, the content or the product use collaborative exercises and encourage talking on the subject - this is indicative of students owning their learning • Mix of formal and informal seating, and a break out space in the back of the room • Offer equipment to help them support their own learning (access to the internet perhaps?)

<p>Developing Responsible and Autonomous Learners: A Key to Motivating Students (McCombs, 2015)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stimulating curiosity in students is key to enabling positive engagement with taught content. • Set clear performance standards from the start. Students need to know exactly what is expected of them, how they will be graded, and what supports will be available to them if they need help learning the information or skills. When teachers communicate performance expectations, they must consider the diverse backgrounds and experiences of each student. Performance outcomes that focus on each student's abilities and strengths lead to more positive student development and engaged learning. • Help students develop a sense of ownership over the learning process. Provide students with choices about how they may demonstrate mastery of a concept, approach particular assignments, work independently or with peers, and achieve at their competency levels. When students have the opportunity to be involved in making these choices, they take more responsibility for their own learning. • Encourage students to assess their own learning progress by using charts or keeping journals, so they can evaluate the progress they are making as they acquire relevant knowledge and skills.
<p>Positive behaviour support: Behavioural expectations (NSW Government Department of Education, 2022)</p>	<p>Behaviour expectations are tools that encourage positive behaviour – they are standards of conduct which might take the form of 'dos and don'ts' or procedures to follow in certain situations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Broadly stated: 3-5 expectations • Apply to all situations and settings • Communicate the expected behaviour • Usually whole school agreed. Rules • Align with expectations • Are specific, observable, and positively stated • Are a replacement for inappropriate behaviours • 1-3 rules for each expectation
<p>Factors Influencing Teachers in Engaging with University Outreach: Is it Just Cost? (Glover et al., 2016)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Teacher objectives often student inspiration over acquiring knowledge • Finances a big concern/ barrier to attendance, including transport costs • Science Teachers motivated to arrange attendance once convinced of its value • Not unusual for teachers to pull out of free events - financial cost informs perception of value
<p>Perceptions of Higher Education Outreach (Office for Students, 2019)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Teachers specifically are looking for something that feels like it is bespoke and tailored to their school. This should be reflected in the way that the programme is communicated and marketed. • Parents have a big impact on student perception of subjects and education/ training/ career paths
<p>Understanding the evaluation of access and participation outreach interventions for under 16 year olds (Carlone & Johnson, 2007)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 'Theory of change' as a thinking tool to understand and plan how changes in knowledge, attitudes or behaviours might be achieved through specific activities and to challenge underpinning assumptions; • Don't measure 'aspiration rising', interest in HE <- think about intermediate measures of success (increased self-efficacy, confidence, career planning skills etc)

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